

REVITALIZATION OF PASIR JAMBAK BEACH BY MANGROVE CULTIVATION AS ECOTOURISM AND BIOCONSERVATION AREA FOR SHOREBIRDS

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Mangrove forests form a natural protective barrier against these as well as providing an ecotourism-based destination or a site for educational ecological tours. Such activities can support mangrove conservation and biodiversity management programs (Raynaldo et al., 2020). In Indonesia, the use of mangroves as recreation sites has been reported by numerous authors (Hakim et al., 2007; Hakim et al., 2012; Fahrian et al., 2015; Siagian et al., 2015). There are numerous potential attractive and educational ecotourism programs in mangrove-based tourism destinations, but so far, few programs have been implemented. This includes mangrove sightseeing, visiting aquaculture, fishing, canoeing, bird watching and volunteering in mangrove conservation programs (Hakim et al., 2017). Sumatra is an important stopover site for migratory shorebirds, but the available information is limited to population dynamics and distributional records (Silvius, 1988; Verheugt et al., 1993; Iqbal et al., 2010; Crossland et al., 2012; Putra et al., 2015; Putra et al., 2017). Mangrove forest and intertidal mudflat along the eastern coastline of Sumatra provides habitat for migratory shorebirds is being converted to human land-use (Silvius, 1988; Verheugt et al., 1993; Iqbal et al., 2010; Crossland et al., 2012; Putra et al., 2015; Putra et al., 2017). On the other hand, the west coastline of Sumatra is characterized by steep terrain associated with the Bukit Barisan mountain chain, surf zones and limited intertidal surface. These conditions are less favorable for sheltering shorebirds (Ripley, 1944; Crossland et al., 2006; Janra et al., 2018). In research from Janra et al. (2018) state that Pasir Jambak Beach were bordered with nipah palm swamp formation. No mangrove vegetation was observed in this site. In this research, mangrove planting was carried out as ecotourism and bioconservation for shorebirds. Some reasons for this research, because the mangrove vegetation on Pasir Jambak Beach has not been observed, so it can reveal mangrove planting that has the potential to be used as ecotourism and bioconservation for shorebirds.

Based on the mangrove density value, the contribution of stands with dbh >10 cm (trees) is very small and categorized as low (Wicaksono et al., 2016). However, stands with diameter <10 cm have a good ability of regeneration. The existence of approximately 260 ha of mangrove forests (Raynaldo et al., 2020) and coral reefs along the coastal area can support marine habitats and fishing activities. Many studies have shown a strong relationship between the presence of mangroves and fish catch as well as shrimp catch, which are influenced by the relative abundance

of mangroves in an area (Manson et al., 2005; Meynecke et al., 2007; Nagelkerken et al., 2008). The importance of mangrove forest habitats for aquatic life function of mangrove forests as drivers of nearshore fishery production, conservation efforts are needed in order to increase sustainable fisheries products. Mangrove forest conservation should involve local communities and the government, because they have local wisdom that has been tested for a long time in preserving mangrove forests (Mukhtar et al., 2021).

According to Ramadan (2016), states that Pasir Jambak is a coastal area that has a relatively wide, sand-substrate beach along the coastline. This location area is one of the areas for tourism, settlements and traffic activities of fishing boats with the characteristic conditions of waves and tidal currents that are quite large. WTO (2010) stated the biodiversity is a direct attraction of nature-based tourism products, such as tourism in protected and ecotourism areas. However, the loss of biodiversity due to human activities is seen as a potential threat to tourist attractions in this mangrove ecotourism area. Malik et al. (2018) reported that loss of mangrove vegetation area has caused fauna that inhabited in this mangrove ecotourism area in low diversity, consequential difficult to found mammals (such as monkey and bat), while bird and reptile were found to be only 4 species (bird: *Collocalia* sp., *Ciconia* sp., *Halycon* sp., and *Egretta* sp.; reptile: *Varanus* sp., *Dasia* sp., *Cerberus* sp., and *Chrysopelea* sp.). Hakim (2017) demonstrated that the change of habitat, degradation, and deforestation due to conversion into other land uses has consequences to reduce reproduction success and decline population survival which may lead to species and population disappear. Many wildlife, such as mammals, reptiles, and birds inhabit in mangrove areas will seek refuge and new habitat (Malik et al., 2019).

Environmental factors other than prey abundance affect species richness and abundance of shorebirds. Water depth has a direct effect on feeding activities of shorebirds. Salinity can affect surface-feeding shorebirds because different species of aquatic invertebrates exhibit differences in salinity tolerance (Liang et al., 2002). Correlation analysis revealed that shorebird species richness at mangrove wetlands correlated significantly and positively with mudflat area. Shorebird numbers were also significantly and positively correlated with mudflat area. But, species richness and abundance of shorebirds were the lowest in an area because of smallest area both mangrove and intertidal flat. Surely, wetland area was an important factor affecting shorebird distribution (Zou et al., 2008).

Mangroves provide an ecotourism-based destination that can support mangrove conservation and biodiversity management programs, as well as an important stopover for migrating shorebirds. The importance of mangrove forest habitat for aquatic life functions as an activator of mangrove forests, conservation efforts are needed. Pasir Jambak Beach does not have mangrove vegetation, but has a relatively wide sand substrate along the coastline. Environmental factors other than prey

abundance affect species richness and abundance of shorebirds. The richness of shorebirds in the mangrove wetlands is significantly and positively correlated with the mud plain area. Obviously, the vast wetlands are important factors that affect the distribution of shorebirds.

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